

BEHAVIORAL ASPECTS OF INTERNET BANKING USERS AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Internet banking is electronic bank that provide financial services to the customers. The main objective of the study is to find out the behavior aspect of users towards internet banking. The study was based on structured questionnaire with a sample of 100 respondents. The data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis, chi-square test and Friedman ranking test. The study concluded that there is significant association between the behavior aspects of users and their level of awareness, preference towards internet banking. E-Banking is a 24 hours behavior service was the first attracting factor of the users towards internet banking.

Key Words: Banking, users, Behavior, Awareness, Preference, Satisfaction, Online, Internet, Satisfaction, Customers etc.

Introduction:

Internet banking is an umbrella term for the process by which a customer may perform banking transactions electronically without visiting a brick-and-mortar institution. Internet banking is electronic bank that provide financial services to the customers. Internet banking facilitates an effective payment and accounting system thereby enhancing the speed of delivery of banking services considerably. It has improved efficiency and convenience, it has posed several challenges to the regulators and supervisors. Moreover, customer expectation for quality, service, and value are rising continually.

Definition of e – Banking:

"Banking transactions done through internet is known as e- banking"

Types of Electronic Banking in India:

The following three basic kinds of internet banking:

- ✓ **Informational:** This is the basic level of electronic banking. Risk involved in such kind of internet banking is relatively low as informational systems typically have no path between the server and the bank's internal network.
- ✓ **Communicative:** This type of electronic banking system allows some interaction between the bank's systems and the customer. The interaction may be limited to e-mail, account inquiry, loan applications, or static file updates etc. Because these servers may have a path to the bank's internal networks, the risk is higher with this configuration than with informational systems. Appropriate controls need to be in place to prevent, monitor and alert management of any unauthorized attempt to access the bank's internal networks and computer systems. Virus controls becomes much more critical in this environment.
- ✓ **Transactional:** This level of electronic banking allows customers to execute transactions. Hence there exists relationship between the server and the bank's or outsourcer's internal network, this is the highest risk architecture and must have the strongest controls. Customer transactions include accessing accounts, paying bills, transferring funds, etc.

Statement of the Problem:

Due to awareness of the internet and its usage, people are willing to avail the banking services from the place of stay. They don't want to go to the bank to avail the banking facility. Due to various government norms, now the young people are also opening and avail the banking services. They want to make all banking transaction from the home. But the problem in using the internet facility and availing banking facility is seen little bit complicated due to lack of awareness and interest among users. So this study wants to know the behavioural aspects of users respondents towards internet banking. This may help the banking in designing the products, applications, and maintenance of server used by banks.

Objectives of the Study:

This study centred on the *users* who use banking services through mobile internet. Following are the objectives of the study:

- ✓ To know the level of awareness possessed by users towards internet banking.
- ✓ To know the users preference and its level towards internet banking

- ✓ To study the satisfaction level in using the internet banking among the users respondents.
- ✓ To rank the behavioral aspects of users towards internet banking.

Methodology of the Study:

Sampling Design:

Thanjavur and Tiruchirappalli District is the study area. A total of 100 respondents are taken as sample. These respondents were randomly selected in Thanjavur and Tiruchirappalli District. Primary data is collected through well-structured questionnaire. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools.

Statistical Tools Used:

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test
- ✓ Friedman Ranking Test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Thanjavur and Tiruchirappalli District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Personal Profile of the Respondents:

Table No.1 reveals the personal profile of the respondents of the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study it has been identified that most (53%) of the respondent are male, (46%) of the respondents belong to semi-urban area, (49%) of the respondents came to know about the internet banking through friends/relatives, (45%) of the respondents use internet banking frequently and (39%) of the respondents are attracted through 24 hours service of the internet banking.

Table 1: Personal Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	53	53
Female	47	47
Place of Residence		
Rural	22	22
Semi-urban	46	46
Urban	32	32
Source of Knowledge		
Advertisement	25	25
Friends/ Relatives	49	49
Officers	26	26
Usage		
Occasionally	25	25
Frequently	45	45
Very Frequently	30	30
Factors		
Easy Usage	15	15
24 hours Service	39	39
Safety & Security	26	26
Time Save	20	20

Source: Primary Data, Values are calculated using SPSS.

Table 2: Users respondents and level of awareness towards Internet Banking

Teen Age	Level of awareness			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Male	8 (15.14)	27 (50.9)	18 (33.96)	53 (100)	6.325	5.991
Female	12 (25.53)	26 (55.53)	09 (19.14)	47 (100)		
Total	20	53	27	100		

Inference:

The table value of chi-square for 2 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 5.991. Since the calculated value of chi-square value is 6.325 greater than the table value 5.991, the difference is insignificant. So we can reject the null hypothesis, (i.e.) there is significant association between the behavior aspects of users and their level of awareness towards internet banking.

Table 3: Users respondents and level of preference towards internet banking

Teen Age	Level of preference			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Male	7 (13.21)	29 (54.72)	17 (32.07)	53 (100)	9.325	5.991
Female	9 (19.15)	29 (61.7)	9 (19.15)	47 (100)		
Total	16	58	26	100		

Inference:

The table value of chi-square for 2 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 5.991. Since the calculated value of chi-square value is 9.325 greater than the table value 5.991, the difference is insignificant. So we can reject the null hypothesis, (i.e.) there is significant association between the behavior aspect of users and their level of preference towards internet banking.

Table 4: Users respondents and level of satisfaction towards Internet Banking

Teen Age	Level of Satisfaction			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Male	17 (32.07)	19 (35.86)	17 (32.07)	53 (100)	3.325	5.991
Female	12 (25.53)	29 (61.07)	06 (13.4)	47 (100)		
Total	29	48	23	150		

Inference:

The table value of chi-square for 2 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 5.991. Since the calculated value of chi-square value is 3.325 greater than the table value 5.991, the difference is significant. So we can accept the null hypothesis, (i.e.) there is no significant association between the behavior aspects of users and their level of satisfaction towards internet banking.

Table 5: Behavioural aspects of Users towards internet banking–Friedman Rank Test

Factors	A	NANDA	DA	Total	Average Rank	Rank
Easy To Use Of E-Banking Services	37	39	24	100	4.46	4
E-Banking Provides Safety And Security	30	42	28	100	5.24	2
E-Banking Provides Up-To-Date & Accurate Information	223	128	17	100	4.36	5
E-Banking Is Time Saving Process	46	34	20	100	4.69	3
E-Banking Is 24 Hours Available Service	68	24	8	100	5.26	1

The table no.5 shows that E-Banking is 24 hours available service was the first attracting factor of the users towards internet banking. E-Banking Provides Safety and Security was ranked as the second factor to choose the insurance company, E-Banking Is Time Saving Process was ranked as third factor, Easy To Use Of E-Banking Services was ranked as fourth factor and E-Banking Provides Up-To-Date & Accurate Information was the fifth factor. From the Friedman Ranking test it is found that majority of the users are attracted towards internet banking through 24 hours service of E-Banking.

Finding:

- ✓ Awareness level about the internet banking among the users are not same. Awareness level differs from person to person and most of the users are having moderate level of awareness towards internet banking.
- ✓ In terms of prefer of users toward internet banking are differ from person to person. Shad raw of awareness among the users is clearly reflected in the level o preference towards internet banking users an having only moderate prefer towards internet banking.
- ✓ While studying about the level of satisfaction attain by the users respondents, it is clear they don't have any significant satisfaction in internet banking.
- ✓ In analyzing the behavior aspects of users response towards internet banking, it is evident that 24 Hour service providing is given much importance respondents feels that usage of internet banking is safe with security. Respondent feels that, bank are not updating the software and browser frequently

Suggestions:

User's awareness towards internet banking is moderate. So banks can start the campaign to promote the awareness level about the internet banking among the general public. Banks are suggested to concentrate on introducing new apps and security systems. Satisfaction level on using the internet banking among the users respondents is not high. Banks need to find the reason for the non-satisfied customer and tries to satisfy the customer in retaining in the same hub.

Conclusion:

Internet Banking is one of the most innovative, widely accepted, highly appreciated and non-discriminatory banking credit products. Behavior of users towards banking services has changed tremendously.

Not only the users but the internet banking should reach each and every people in India. There is a need for educating the customers to bank through internet and close supervision also required. The gap can be removed through two methods one is minimizing the minimum criteria and another is educating for utilization of internet banking. Internet banking will be successful for banks only when they have commitment to e-banking along with a deeper understanding of customer needs.

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